

Silex sandfilter

The quality requirements for the effluent wastewater from municipal and industrial wastewater treatment plants are increasingly strict. The Silex sandfilter is a reliable filter system for many applications among others to meet these specific requirements.

General information

The Silex sandfilter is a deep-bed type upflow filter with continuous filtration capability. Its effectiveness lies in the fact that there are no shutdowns necessary for backwash cycles for the sand washing process.

The inlet is at the bottom of the filter and as the feed flows upwards through the sand bed, the solids are retained in the filter sand. The filtrate exits over a weir at the top. The sand sinks and gets into the airlift pipe in the center of the filter. It transports the mix upwards to the sandwasher. The solids are separated from the sand in the washer. The clean sand falls back onto the sand bed thus creating the internal sand circulation.

The modular design ensures the optimal treatment of any throughput. The filter is available in two versions, as a concrete basin and as a steel tank design.

The free-standing filter consists of a cylindrical tank in stainless steel provided with flanged connection for feed, filtrate discharge, wash water discharge and drain. The filter is provided with a welded-on plate, suitable for fastening of a side-mounted access walkway. Adjustable bolts are provided for levelling the filter.

The filter is delivered with internal parts consisting of water distributor, sand distributor, sand washer, guide tube and air-lift pump.

In the supply for the concrete version each filter internal and bottom cone consist of the following items: bottom cone with anchor/levelling bolts and anchor/joint bolts, internal parts comprising inlet pipe, water distributor, sand distributor, sand washer and airlift pump.

General dimensions and construction materials

Main material	EN.14301 or EN1.4404/EN1.4571
Max. allowed temperature	60°C
Max. Wind load	
Rubber couplings	EPDM
Air-lift pump	EN.14301 or EN1.4404/EN1.4571
Head loss pipe	PVC
Sand washer	Glass fiber reinforced composite

Technical specification

Free-standing filters									
Model	Drawing Nr.	Area (m ²)	D (mm)	H1 (mm)	H2 (mm)	Feed (DN)	Filtrate (DN)	Reject (DN)	Drain
3.15	H-3-15	2,86	1920	5065	6300	DN150	DN150	DN65	R2"
3.20	H-3-20	2,86	1920	5565	6800	DN150	DN150	DN65	R2"
3.25	H-3-25	2,86	1920	6065	7300	DN150	DN150	DN65	R2"
5.15	H-5-15	4,87	2500	5565	6800	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"
5.20	H-5-20	4,87	2500	6065	7300	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"
5.25	H-5-25	4,87	2500	6565	7800	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"
7.15	H-7-15	7,03	3000	6065	7300	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"
7.20	H-7-20	7,03	3000	6565	7800	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"
7.25	H-7-25	7,03	3000	7065	8300	DN200	DN200	DN65	R2"

Concrete version									
5.15 C	H-5-15-C	5,8	2430	5183	5355	DN200	-	DN65	-
5.20 C	H-5-20-C	5,8	2430	5683	5855	DN200	-	DN65	-
5.25 C	H-5-25-C	5,8	2430	6183	6355	DN200	-	DN65	-